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Taxonomy of DHT, mapping to the assessment framework

Deliverable 2.1: Taxonomy of DHT for assessment purposes

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Abstract

This Deliverable, D2.1 Taxonomy of Digital Health Technologies (DHT) for Assessment Purposes, provides an overview of the first version of a taxonomy that shall enable us to further develop assessment requirements for assessing DHT. Based on different methodologies (survey HTA agencies, scoping review), a first version of a taxonomy was developed, that is based on the following criteria: (1) purpose of the DHT (determining which outcomes are relevant), (2) DHT-relevant dimensions of “risk” (patient vulnerability as well as directness of DHT to drive decisions), combined in a matrix determining assessment requirements, and (3) the use of AI. Each criterion contains different subcategories.

Usage note: This taxonomy presents a conceptual model for the landscape of DHT that is in the scope of the ASSESS-DHT project. It has been produced early in the project to guide in the Identification of relevant areas for DHT assessment. It will be piloted and validated through use cases within the project work plan and is therefore subject to change in the light of this experience. A validated taxonomy will be included as an annex to the final assessment manual.”

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMA	American Medical Association
AQuAS	Agency for Quality and Assessment of Catalonia
BfArM	German Federal Institute for Drugs and Medical Devices
DHT	Digital health technologies
DiGAs	Digital health applications as defined according to the German Regulation “Digitale Gesundheitsanwendungen-Verordnung – DiGAV”
DiGAV	Digitale Gesundheitsanwendungen-Verordnung (German Regulation on DiGAs)
EU	European Union
HAS	Haute Autorité de Santé
HTA	Health technology assessment
ICER	Institute for Clinical and Economic Review
IMDRF	International Medical Device Regulators Forum
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
PHTI	Peterson Health Technology Institute
HTAR	Regulation (EU) 2021/2282 on Health Technology Assessment
SaMD	Software as Medical Device
SiMD	Software in a Medical Device
WHO	World Health Organization

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Understanding the diversity of digital health technologies (DHT) is crucial for addressing the variation in assessment approaches needed for these technologies. A taxonomy can help group DHT according to criteria relevant for the purpose of health technology assessments (HTA) in healthcare systems. Existing taxonomies, including their criteria for grouping DHT often follow different logics and may not fully address the latest innovations in DHT, making them to some extent inappropriate for assessment purposes.

This Deliverable, D2.1 Taxonomy of Digital Health Technologies (DHT) for Assessment Purposes, provides an overview of the first version of a taxonomy that shall enable us to further develop evidence requirements for assessing DHT.

By examining various classification, categorization, and grouping schemes used for different purposes, we aimed at developing a taxonomy for DHT that is:

1. suitable for highlighting the extent to which HTA is necessary for different DHT categories,
2. suitable for characterizing assessment requirements.

For the latter, the categories need to be broad enough to encompass a wide range of DHT, yet specific enough to highlight the assessment and evidence requirements for particular categories. In addition, the categories should be versatile enough to include DHT with mixed functions as well as future DHT that are not yet known.

Based on different methodologies (survey HTA agencies, scoping review), a first version of a taxonomy was developed, that is based on a set of criteria to facilitate HTA: (medical) purpose, “risk”, and the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI). Each criterion contains different subcategories. The main medical purposes to be considered are prevention, monitoring, prognosis, diagnosis, and treatment. The risk classification was – beyond the usage of the term in the MDR – developed as a 3 x 3 matrix made up of vulnerability of patients (state of healthcare situation/condition), which includes the groups ‘critical, serious, and non-serious’ on the one hand, and the medical intention (directness) subdivided into the groups ‘inform, drive and make clinical management/ patient management’ on the other hand. The 3 x 3 matrix results in 4 requirement levels. The additional criterium AI was split into no, static, dynamic and adaptive.

To validate taxonomy, the developed set of criteria is being tested for technologies, already evaluated by HTA agencies. In addition, the initial version of the taxonomy will be piloted within this project (Work Package 5) to evaluate its usefulness and usability for its primary target audience: developers and assessors of DHT. The taxonomy will be further refined and enhanced as the project progresses.

1 Introduction

The urgency to transform healthcare systems is growing, as is the use of a wide variety of both proven and unproven digital health technologies. DHT are expected to enhance accessibility, affordability, and quality of healthcare (Ahern, 2006). However, these technologies may differ from traditional healthcare and health technologies in terms of their technological features, the speed of their development, and the complexity of integrating them into routine care (Stelk, 2006; The Lancet, 2018).

Understanding the diversity of DHT is crucial for addressing the variation in assessment approaches needed for these technologies. A taxonomy can help group them according to criteria relevant for assessments, such as complexity, goal, and the intended impact on the healthcare system (e.g., improving health, efficiency, access). Other factors include the level of risk involved in their use, and their incremental evolution, particularly with AI-powered technologies. The evaluation strategies for DHT may also depend on whether they are designed to strengthen the demand side (e.g., improving patient access) or the supply side (e.g., enhancing healthcare delivery) of the health sector (Expert Panel on Effective Ways of Investing in Health, 2018).

Several frameworks and taxonomies have been developed for different purposes, from regulatory frameworks to coverage and reimbursement in publicly financed health systems. Many of these are risk-based, such as the Software as a Medical Device (SaMD) concept, which classifies technologies into four risk classes (IMDRF, 2014). The NICE Evidence Standards Framework aligns types of digital technologies with the required levels of evidence (NICE 2018, 2021, 2022). Meanwhile, the World Health Organization (WHO) uses a taxonomy based on how technologies support the needs of health systems (WHO, 2023). Classifications of DHT ranges from broad to specific definitions. For example, the German Federal Institute for Drugs and Medical Devices (BfArM) has implemented a fast-track pathway for assessing certain digital health applications (DiGAs)¹. France has introduced several early access programs for medical devices, each with distinct objectives. Among these is the Transitional Coverage for Digital Health Applications (PECAN) program, launched in 2022. PECAN targets digital medical devices designed for therapeutic purposes or patient monitoring (Martin et al., 2024).

A recently published policy analysis has identified different assessment frameworks for such digital health applications in the European Union (EU) (Tarricone et al., 2024). Nevertheless from 27 EU member states only Belgium, France, and Germany have established national assessment frameworks combining both regulation and reimbursement, while also complementing the evaluation of clinical benefits with additional assessment domains. The second cluster (Estonia, Finland, the Netherlands, and Spain) comprises countries where assessment frameworks are either not directly linked to reimbursement, lack a centralized unified approach, or are undergoing consolidation. The third cluster

¹ DiGAs are intended to be used by the patient alone or jointly by the patient and healthcare providers. The primary function of the DiGA is based on digital technologies, and the medical purpose must be substantially achieved through the digital primary function, DiGA must be classified as Risk Class I or IIa (since 26. March 2024, also Risk Class IIb) according to the Medical Device Regulation (MDR).

(Denmark, Portugal, Poland, Sweden) is characterized by countries that apply institutional certification processes for DHT. The fourth (Austria, Greece, Italy, Luxembourg and Ireland) and fifth clusters (Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia) include countries that are in the preparatory process of launching a national assessment framework or have no framework in place yet nor planned (Tarricone et al., 2024). Several additional generic or specialized assessment frameworks for DHT have been developed (Vis et al., 2020); however, they often fail to adequately address the unique challenges posed by DHT. These frameworks often do not cover a broad enough spectrum of assessment domains, rendering them unsuitable for use in HTA (Moshi et al. 2018). Existing classifications often follow different logics and may not fully address the latest innovations in DHT, making them unsuitable for our assessment purposes.

When developing a taxonomy, criteria will be defined which are relevant enough to justify placing DHT into different categories with distinct assessment requirements. A hierarchical structure can organize categories in a graded manner, where higher-level categories are linked to methodologically “higher” evidence requirements (e.g., a randomised controlled trial) while requirements for lower-level categories can be lower (e.g., a before-and-after comparison). By examining various classification, categorization, and grouping schemes used for different purposes, we aim to develop a taxonomy for DHT that is:

1. suitable for highlighting the extent to which HTA is necessary for different DHT categories,
2. suitable for characterizing assessment requirements.

For the latter, the categories need to be broad enough to encompass a wide range of DHT, yet specific enough to highlight the assessment and evidence requirements for particular categories.

2 Methods

The development of the first draft of a taxonomy is based on different methodologies:

- (1) A manual web-based search is used to identify several taxonomies that focus on DHT, but may have different purposes;
- (2) Different subgroups/categories used to define a taxonomy have been identified by
 - I. a scoping review of frameworks on methods for assessing digital health technologies
 - II. a survey to HTA agencies.

(1) A manual web-based search is used to identify several taxonomies that focus on DHT but may have different purposes. The following search terms were used to identify taxonomies: Taxonomy OR classification OR grouping AND digital health (technologies).

(2) The scoping review, primarily planned for a landscape and gap analysis of existing value frameworks and methods for assessing DHT (Work package 2.2) was conducted following the guidance provided by

the Joanna Briggs Institute Reviewer Manual (Peters et al., 2017). It also adheres to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Extension for Scoping Reviews guidelines (PRISMA-ScR) (Tricco et al. 2018). A literature search was performed in April 2024 using PubMed and Embase databases. The protocol was registered with the Open Science Framework (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/43RZ5>) on May 2, 2024. This review aimed to identify and map existing frameworks for assessing Digital Health Technologies (DHT), focusing on their availability, purposes, and any guidance related to the assessment of DHT within the domains of the HTA Core Model® (EUnetHTA 2016). Additionally, we examined whether these frameworks distinguish between different groups/classifications of DHT.

(3) A survey was distributed to 30 countries, including the member states of the European Union (N=27), and Norway, Switzerland, as well as the UK, to collect information from HTA agencies and HTA-related organizations (decision-making institutions responsible for HTA appraisal). Depending on the healthcare systems and autonomy of the regions in the countries, the number of HTA agencies varied, e.g., in Spain, eight agencies were contacted.

The questionnaire, developed by TUB and refined by AIHTA and NICE, covered four key areas:

(Part 1) Availability of frameworks/guidance documents/ guidelines to assess Digital Health Technologies (DHT)

(Part 2) Current status of assessed DHT

(Part 3) Current gaps and weaknesses in assessing DHT

(Part 4) Survey for an expert specialized in AI

The following question in key area one was relevant for developing the taxonomy: *Does your agency use a classification/grouping system or a taxonomy to assign specific DHT to groups/levels/tiers within the framework (guidance document/guideline) to determine specific assessment or evidence requirements/standards? (Part 1)*. The entire questionnaire can be found in Appendix 1. Agencies were asked to provide references or documents if available.

To prevent overburdening HTA agencies, partners of ASSESS DHT provided part one of the questionnaire for review to partners of EDiHTA², a project also funded under Horizon Europe, as this project had a similar topic of developing a taxonomy for assessing DHT. Initially it was agreed to share the results of first part of the questionnaire (Availability of frameworks/guidance documents/ guidelines to assess DHT). In July 2024, ASSESS DHT jointly agreed to share all results of the questionnaire with EDiHTA. ASSESS DHT and EDiHTA jointly sent out some clarifying and follow-up questions to HTA agencies in August 2024. Based on the results, the groupings and classifications have been evaluated for their suitability for inclusion in a taxonomy that defines categories with similar assessment requirements for digital health technologies (DHT). Existing taxonomies have been used to develop a

² <https://edihta-project.eu/>

new taxonomy, designed to encompass a broad range of DHT within distinct categories to define respective evidence levels.

3 Results

3.1 Preamble: Guiding principles and definitions

Any taxonomy, including one for “digital health technologies” (DHT), should begin with a clear definition that establishes what constitutes a DHT, and what does not, i.e. what can be excluded. Given that ASSESS DHT is an EU-funded project, it would be most useful to start with a legal definition on the European Union level. However, such a definition is currently lacking. While “assessment” is legally defined in Regulation (EU) 2021/2282 on Health Technology Assessment (HTAR)³, which also mandates joint clinical assessments (at the EU level) for certain high-risk medical devices, including software, no specific definition of DHT is provided.

The closest approximation to a DHT definition can be probably found in the introductory statement on the Commission website stating that “digital health and care refers to tools and services that use information and communication technologies (ICTs) to improve prevention, diagnosis, treatment, monitoring and management of health-related issues and to monitor and manage lifestyle-habits that impact health” (European Commission, 2024). However, this definition is broader than the legal definition used in Regulation (EU) 2017/745 on Medical Devices (MDR), where the term “DHT” is not used, but instead “software” is referenced.

We propose aligning our definition of DHT – and the taxonomy guided by it – with the definition of software under the MDR. Additionally, we suggest harmonizing the terminology used in ASSESS DHT, such as terms related to “purpose” or “risk”, as closely as possible with existing EU regulations to avoid confusion and the need for further clarification regarding potential differences.

In short, according to the MDR (Article 2) a ‘medical device’ is defined as any “... software [...] intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, [...] for one or more of the following specific medical purposes: — diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognosis, treatment or alleviation of disease, — diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, alleviation of, or compensation for, an injury or disability, — investigation, replacement or modification of the anatomy or of a physiological or pathological process or state, [...]”. This definition specifically excludes software intended for monitoring

³ In the Regulation, it says: “[...] (2) Health technology assessment (HTA) is a scientific evidence-based process that allows competent authorities to determine the relative effectiveness of new or existing health technologies. HTA focuses specifically on the added value of a health technology in comparison with other new or existing health technologies. (3) HTA is able to contribute to the promotion of innovation, which offers the best outcomes for patients and society as a whole and is an important tool for ensuring proper application and use of health technologies. (4) HTA can cover both clinical and non-clinical aspects of a health technology, depending on the healthcare system. The Union’s co-funded joint actions on HTA (EUnetHTA Joint Actions) have identified nine domains by reference to which health technologies are assessed. Of these nine domains, four are clinical and five are non-clinical. The four clinical domains of assessment concern the identification of a health problem and current health technology, the examination of the technical characteristics of the health technology under assessment, its relative safety, and its relative clinical effectiveness. The five non-clinical assessment domains concern cost and economic evaluation of a health technology, and its ethical, organisational, social and legal aspects. [...]”

and management lifestyle-habits that impact health. Furthermore, introductory #19 clarifies that “It is necessary to clarify that software in its own right, when specifically intended by the manufacturer to be used for one or more of the medical purposes set out in the definition of a medical device, qualifies as a medical device, while software for general purposes, even when used in a healthcare setting, or software intended for life-style and well-being purposes is not a medical device. The qualification of software, either as a device or an accessory, is independent of the software's location or the type of interconnection between the software and a device.”

Annex I of the MDR clarifies the distinction between “devices that incorporate electronic programmable systems, including software” (commonly referred to as SiMD = Software in a Medical Device) and “software that are devices in themselves” (SaMD = Software as a Medical Device”). Other sources add certain nuances to this distinction (Table 1). We propose primarily limiting the definition — and consequently the taxonomy — to SaMD. In addition, SiMD should be included in the taxonomy if the software is integral to a medical device’s functioning — helping the device achieve its intended medical purpose. This aligns with the HTA approach, as it considers DHT in the context of assessment purposes not only as software but as the "procedure" in which the software is the guiding or major component.

Table 1. Definitions SiMD and SaMD

Term	Definition
Software in a Medical Device (SiMD)	“If the device cannot be used without the software, whether it is running the mechanics or processing the information that is produced.” ICER_PHTI (2023)
Software as a Medical Device (SaMD)	“Software intended to be used for one or more medical purposes that perform these purposes without being part of a hardware medical device.” The software needs to function independently of the existing medical device. IMDRF (2014), FDA

Additionally, the MDR (Annex VI, Part C) addresses when software modifications justify reclassifying as a “new” medical device, which we recommend adopting in ASSESS DHT as well. According to the MDR: “A new UDI-DI [device identifier] shall be required whenever there is a modification that changes: (a) the original performance; (b) the safety or the intended use of the software; (c) interpretation of data. Such modifications include new or modified algorithms, database structures, operating platform, architecture or new user interfaces or new channels for interoperability. Minor software revisions shall require a new UDI-PI [production identifier] and not a new UDI-DI. Minor software revisions are generally associated with bug fixes, usability enhancements that are not for safety purposes, security patches or operating efficiency. Minor software revisions shall be identified by a manufacturer-specific form of identification.”

“Risk” is used by all identified taxonomies, frameworks and legal documents. However, the usage is not always identical. For example, according to the MDR, Article 2, no. 23, ‘risk’ is the combination of the probability of occurrence of harm and the severity of that harm if the medical device is used according to its intended purpose.

The MDR uses classification rules, which group medical devices into four groups. The classification rules are based on the vulnerability of the human body and should consider the potential risks associated with the technical design and manufacture of the devices. They generally take into account the place where the device performs, its action in or on the human body, where it is introduced or applied, and whether a systemic absorption of the substances of which the device is composed, or of the products of metabolism in the human body of those substances occurs.

As these characteristics do usually not apply to software, its risk is based on separate criteria defined in “Rule 11”: “Software intended to provide information which is used to take decisions with diagnosis or therapeutic purposes is classified as class IIa, except if such decisions have an impact that may cause:

- death or an irreversible deterioration of a person's state of health, in which case it is in class III; or
- a serious deterioration of a person's state of health or a surgical intervention, in which case it is classified as class IIb.

Software intended to monitor physiological processes is classified as class IIa, except if it is intended for monitoring of vital physiological parameters, where the nature of variations of those parameters is such that it could result in immediate danger to the patient, in which case it is classified as class IIb.

All other software is classified as class I.”

The IMDRF framework for risk categorisation of software as a medical device (SaMD) (IMDRF, 2014) categorises the risk of software based on the combination of the significance of the information provided by the software to the healthcare decision (which we term “directness”) and the healthcare situation or patient condition (which we term “patient vulnerability”). IMDRF also developed a table for assisting operators in identifying the appropriate risk category for their own product.

Thus, when we use the term risk in this document, it has to be considered that, besides vulnerability, the “directness” of the DHT is taken into account, leading to a matrix structure.

Definition of DHT for HTA purposes

For the taxonomy that classifies DHT according to different criteria suitable for HTA purposes, DHT consider SaMD and SiMD, the latter one in terms of a "procedure" in which the software is the guiding or major component. The software is intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, for at least one of the following specific medical purposes: — diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognosis, treatment or alleviation of disease, — diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, alleviation of, or compensation for, an injury or disability, — investigation, replacement or modification of the anatomy or of a physiological or pathological process or state.

At this stage we exclude DHT

- intended for monitoring and management lifestyle-habits and well-being purposes, even though that might impact health
- intended for general non-medical purposes, even when used in a healthcare setting.

3.2 Existing taxonomies, classifications, groupings for DHT

3.2.1 Results of the web-based search, the scoping review and the HTA agency survey

To guide the development of a taxonomy for HTA purposes we used the results of a literature review, an HTA agency survey and a scoping review of frameworks for assessing DHT.

1) Results of manual web-based search

Based on a manual web-based search identified 12 publications that include at least one kind of classification or grouping system or a taxonomy to differentiate DHT (or groups of DHT) for different purposes. The results can be found in Appendix 2. Depending on the purpose the taxonomies, in 8 publications, a classification, grouping, or taxonomy approach with regard to the criterion risk is used. Some of the publications propose a categorisation according to different risk classes, guidance based on risk categorization, or a categorisation in which risk is explicitly considered as a factor.

2) Results of the scoping review

Regarding the scoping review of frameworks for assessing DHT a total of 3,576 hits (titles and abstracts) were screened, and 89 articles were included in the full-text review. After the additional hand search, in total, 60 articles were included in the synthesis. The detailed results can be found in the report of deliverable 2.2. We only identified 3 out of 60 frameworks, that provided information on whether DHT were classified/grouped and whether this led to different assessment requirements/method in the frameworks. The frameworks usually focus on a specific DHT groups: digital health applications (n=41), DHT in general, without any definition (n=12), telemedicine (n=2), AI (n=1) and other technologies such as precision health innovations or sensor technologies (n=4).

The Evidence Standards Framework for Digital Health Technologies (ESF) of the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE, 2022) classifies DHT by intended purpose to stratify them into tiers based on the potential risk to service users and to the system (Fig. 1). As a result, the evidence level needed for each tier is proportionate to the potential risk to service users for the DHT in that tier. DHT in tier C are additionally split into four classification groups to align with the SaMD classification framework proposed by the International Medical Device Regulators Forum (IMDRF, 2014). In Spain, the Agency for Quality and Assessment of Catalonia (AQuAS) has developed on behalf of the Spanish Ministry of Health and in collaboration with the other regional HTA agencies a methodological framework (Segur-Ferrer et al., 2023) to carry out a comprehensive digital health technology assessment. The classification of DHT is the same considered by NICE.

Figure 1. DHT classified by intended purpose and stratified into risk tiers

Source: NICE, 2022

The main objective of the methodological framework is to enable the value of a given DHT to be identified by considering the main characteristics of this type of technology. Specifically, the methodological framework focuses on: 1) Describing the domains, dimensions and subdimensions to be considered in DHTA. 2) Defining the standards of evidence that DHT should meet based on how the risk arising from their use is classified.

Lantzsch et al. (2022) classified digital health applications according to the attributes: (i) application area, (ii) target group (healthy/acutely ill/chronically ill in stable/unstable status), (iii) function (medical purpose), and (iv) user. It defines three evidence requirement levels (low, medium, high) – thus avoiding the term “risk” – for each DiGA group which are determined by the two attributes “target group” and “function” (medical purpose) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Proposal for DiGA directory with criterion values and correspondence to evidence requirement levels

i. Scope (according to ICD-10)	ii. Target group	iii. Function of the DiGA		iv. User	seq. No.
...	0 Healthy without known risk factors	0 Documentation		1 Only patients or relatives	001 002 003 ...
Exx Endocrine, nutritional and metabolic diseases	1 Healthy with risk factors	1 Information		2 Patients & Service Providers	001 002 003 ...
Fxx Mental and behavioural disorders	2 acutely ill, not life-threatening	2 Prevention, prediction, prognosis		3 Service providers only	...
Hxx Diseases of the eye and ear	3 chronically ill, stable state of health	3 Examination of a physiological or pathological process or condition			...
Ixx Diseases of the circulatory system	4 highly vulnerable/ unstable health status	Detection (diagnosis)	4 Diagnosis		...
Oxx Pregnancy, Birth and Postpartum		Supervision (monitoring)	5 Simple monitoring		...
			6 Complex monitoring		
...		Treatment (therapy)	7 Indirect intervention (self-management)		...
			8 Direct intervention (change in health conditions)		

Light blue filling= Low requirement level; Medium blue filling= Medium requirement level; Dark blue filling= High requirement level

Source: Lantzsch et al. 2022

Since March 2024, the German DiGA approach, initially including certain digital health applications of risk class I and IIa was expanded to risk class IIb according to the Medical Device Regulation (MDR). DiGAs are intended to be used by the patient alone or jointly by the patient and healthcare providers.

Their primary function must be based on digital technologies, and their medical purpose must be substantially achieved through the digital primary function. According to the risk class different evidence and assessment requirements arise: 1) Endpoints to be assessed: DiGAs of MDR-based risk class I and IIa are allowed to provide evidence on the positive effects on care as either medical benefit or patient-relevant structural and procedural improvements. The latter includes improvements regarding coordination of treatment processes, adherence, access to care, health literacy, patient autonomy, therapy-related expenses and burdens for patients and their relatives. Retrospective comparative study designs are allowed. Nevertheless, DIGAs of risk class IIb must use prospective comparative study designs for assessing the medical benefit, while assessing the benefit only based on patient-relevant structural and procedural improvements is not allowed (DiGAV, 2024).

3) Results of the HTA agency survey

A total of 23 HTA agencies and HTA-related organizations (decision-making institutions responsible for HTA appraisal) completed the questionnaire. The countries that responded and took part in the survey were: Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Malta, Norway⁴, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom. Cyprus reported that no framework is available.

In the following chapters we will only use the term HTA agency, which includes HTA agencies and HTA bodies responsible for the elaboration of HTA reports to inform access decisions, at different levels of the healthcare systems they serve. The survey was used for different work packages and deliverables of the project (2.1, 2.2 and 4). The relevant question in connection with the development of a taxonomy for DHT for HTA purposes was, whether HTA agencies use a classification/grouping system or a taxonomy to assign specific DHT to groups/levels/tiers to determine specific assessment or evidence requirements.

More than half of all agencies participating in the survey (61%) stated that they do not have any classification or taxonomy that structures DHT into specific groups or levels to determine specific assessment or evidence requirements. About 35% state that their guidelines include a classification of DHT and that they take this into account in their assessment.

However, overall, there are only two grouping systems that are used to determine specific assessment or evidence requirements. Overall, the Spanish HTA agencies that responded (n=4) as well as Wales and Scotland use the same grouping criteria as NICE. The second system is the German system, differentiating between the risk classes according to MDR, and defining different evidence requirements as described earlier.

The French PECAN approach developed to determine reimbursement eligibility includes therapeutic or telemonitoring DMDs for individual use (up to class III, MDR). It uses a functional classification to facilitate and structure interactions between the various stakeholders. Nevertheless, there is currently no link to specific requirements for assessment. Assessment principles established by the Medical

⁴ The agency of this country did not fill out the questionnaire but answered a few questions via email.

Device and Health Technology Evaluation Committee (CNEDiMTS) to determine the reimbursement eligibility of medical devices for individual use are used (Martin et al., 2024).

The Belgium Validation Pyramid is not used to divide DHT into different groups based on risk class, claimed value, functionalities etc. Rather, it is a procedure with the aim to define (progressively) quality requirements, including security, privacy, interoperability, usability, and reimbursement requirements and to facilitate the integration of mobile health apps in the Belgian healthcare system (mhealth Belgium).

3.3 The taxonomy

Based on the guiding principle and definition of DHT and health technology assessment (HTA), SaMD and, to a lesser extent, SiMD are the focus of the development of the taxonomy that is suitable for HTA purposes. A subdivision into often used, but not legally defined individual DHT types (e.g. telemedicine, mhealth) is not taken into consideration since each DHT type can serve different purposes, and may fall into different risk classes. Including such distinctions could lead to overly complex classifications without a clear HTA-specific rationale. Function/purpose in combination with the risk to the user, nevertheless, plays a direct role in determining the level of evidence, which is then required to judge the balance of risks and benefits (usually based on an appropriate level of certainty). Those can be then linked to distinct evidence standards.

Therefore, the taxonomy is built using a set of criteria designed to facilitate HTA. It focuses on the aspects of

- ▶ (medical) purpose,
- ▶ DHT-relevant dimensions of “risk”, and
- ▶ the use of AI.

3.3.1 Criterion: (Medical) Purpose

Given the wide array of DHT, assessing DHT from an HTA perspective presents unique challenges. A key challenge among these concerns is the considerable variation in the medical purposes of DHT. The purpose of a DHT plays a critical role in determining the outcomes for which evidence is required – and thereby to a certain extent also for the type of evidence required or at least acceptable⁵. Therefore, the first step is to categorize DHT based on their purpose, which generally refers to the medical purpose the DHT serves (IMDRF, 2014). Evidence requirements of DHT may vary depending on their purpose (e.g. diagnosis versus treatment) within different stages of the care pathway. The categorization according to the DHT’s purpose should directly determine the type of “outcome” to look at (e.g. diagnostic vs.

⁵ Just as an example (from NICE’s manual to health technology assessments (2022)): “3.3.2 The preferred source of evidence depends on the specific use being considered. For relative treatment effects there is a strong preference for high-quality randomised controlled trials (RCTs). Non-randomised studies may complement RCTs when evidence is limited or form the primary source of evidence when there is no RCT evidence. For diagnostic technologies, there is a preference for end-to-end studies. When there is insufficient evidence from these studies, a linked evidence approach should be taken. For clinical outcomes such as natural history, treatment patterns or patient experiences, real-world evidence may be preferred.”

therapeutic). According to the MDR, we propose a differentiation between the following five purposes: prevention, monitoring, prediction/prognosis (we suggest combining them), diagnosis and treatment, while alleviation of disease and compensation for injury or disability are part of the treatment purpose. Outside the scope of the taxonomy are therefore those digital technologies without a medical purpose, e.g. for operational purposes of hospitals (left side of Figure 1). The purpose/function ‘Health & Wellness’ is also excluded, as it falls outside the remit of the MDR (see preamble).

3.3.2 Criterion: Risk

The criterion risk differentiation is necessary to determine evidence requirements for the assessment of DHT, particularly the minimum methodological level of required/ acceptable evidence (e.g. resulting from a well conducted RCT, conducted in a blinded way and analysed according to the intention-to-treat principle, rather than just any RCT) to evaluate the balance of benefits and risks with the appropriate level of certainty. The risk (both the likelihood of harm occurring and the severity of harm if it does occur) must be weighed against the benefit – this is why risk is so important: If there is high risk (either because of the probability or because of the harm if it occurs), the benefit must also be high. To be sure that it is large, we need reliable, valid evidence, which in turn requires adherence to methodologically high assessment standards.

For the *directness* criterion, which is based on the significance of information collected or produced by DHT for health care decisions, a distinction is made between ‘Inform’, ‘Drive’ and ‘Make’ clinical management by health care providers and patients (Table 2). Those display the levels of impact on the patient or public health but necessitate accurate information provided on the ability of the DHT to avoid death, long-term disability or other serious deterioration of health, mitigating public health. ‘Inform’ includes DHT that provide information to inform health care provider or patients regarding clinical management of a disease or conditions. ‘Drive’ contains DHT that provide information to drive clinical management of a disease or conditions, while ‘Make’ infers that the information provided by the DHT will be used to take an immediate or near-term action by the provider or patient (IMDRF, 2014). Overall, we did not consider the criterion ‘user’, i.e. whether only patients, service providers or both are involved in the use of the DHT as this criterion is inherent to the risk groups considered.

Table 2. Definitions of the criterium “significance of information provided” (directness)

Significance of information provided (directness)	Definition	Source
Inform (clinical management/patient management)	DHT provide information to inform clinical or patient management of a disease or conditions	IMDRF (2014)
Drive (clinical management/patient management)	DHT that provide information to drive clinical or patient management of a disease or conditions	IMDRF (2014)
Make (treat, diagnose)	DHT that provide information to treat or diagnose a disease or condition (information provided will be used to take an immediate or near-term action by health care provider/patient)	IMDRF (2014)

The additional grouping criterion *Vulnerability of patients* reflects the disease severity and primarily includes the condition or disease for which the DHT is meant to be applied (Table 3). Different categorizations exist which incorporates the three-level notion laid out in Annex VIII, Rule 11 of the MDR, a differentiation between critical, serious, and non-serious conditions. The grouping also used by IMDRF is based on considerations such as the progression or stage of the disease (IMDRF 2014, 2024, Lantzsch et al. 2022).

Table 3. Definition of the criterion: Patient vulnerability

Patient Vulnerability (state of healthcare situation/condition)	Definition	Source
Critical	Situations or conditions where accurate and/or timely diagnosis or treatment action is vital to avoid death, long-term disability or other serious deterioration of health of an individual patient or to mitigating impact to public health.	IMDRF (2014), IMDRF (2024)
Serious	Situations/conditions where accurate diagnosis or treatment is of vital importance to avoid unnecessary interventions or timely interventions are important to mitigate long term irreversible consequences on an individual patient’s health condition or public health.	IMDRF (2014), IMDRF (2024)
Non-Serious	Situations or conditions where an accurate diagnosis and treatment is important but not critical for interventions to mitigate long term irreversible consequences on an individual patient's health condition or public health.	IMDRF (2014), IMDRF (2024)

Combining significance of information (directness) and state of healthcare situation/ condition (vulnerability) into requirement levels

The two criteria, i.e. *DHT’s significance of information to health care decision for health care the provider or patient (directness)* and *vulnerability of patients*, each stratified into three levels based on its potential risk to patients, are combined into a 3 x 3 matrix with 9 combinations.

As outlined above, the two criteria are combined in a 3 x 3 matrix, resulting in 9 fields, which in turn are allocated into four requirement levels (based on the risk categorisation of the IMDRF, 2014). The lowest level (“I”) as a combination of both risk criteria is associated with DHT that do not directly affect clinical care and are either meant to inform clinical management or drive clinical management in a non-serious condition (non-serious vulnerability). The highest requirement level (“IV”) includes those DHT that deliver an intervention or directly impact clinical decision-making for serious or urgent condition (critical vulnerability). This also includes situations with the potential for serious morbidity or mortality. Evidence requirements in assessing DHT must be higher for DHT intended for instance for patients with critical health conditions (highly vulnerable people). For further definitions of the three types of vulnerability, see table 4 (based on IMDRF, 2014).

Table 4. Requirement levels as the result of the directness and vulnerability matrix

Vulnerability of patients (state of healthcare situation/condition)	'Directness' Intention of using DHT-collected or -produced information for health care decisions (by health care provider or patient)		
	Make (treat or diagnose)	Drive (clinical) management	Inform (clinical) management
Critical	<p>IV</p> <p>Provides information to treat or diagnose a disease or conditions in a critical situation or condition</p> <p>→ very high impact on patient or public health</p>	<p>III</p> <p>Provides information to drive clinical management of a disease or conditions in a critical situation or condition</p> <p>→ high impact on patient or public health</p>	<p>II</p> <p>Provides information to inform clinical management of a disease or conditions in a critical situation or condition</p> <p>→ medium impact on patient or public health</p>
Serious	<p>III</p> <p>Provides information to treat or diagnose a disease or conditions in a serious situation or condition</p> <p>→ high impact on patient or public health</p>	<p>II</p> <p>Provides information to drive clinical management of a disease or conditions in a serious situation or condition</p> <p>→ medium impact on patient or public health</p>	<p>I</p> <p>Provides information to inform clinical management for a disease or conditions in a serious situation or condition</p> <p>→ low impact on patient or public health</p>
Non-serious	<p>II</p> <p>Provides information to treat or diagnose a disease or conditions in a non-serious situation or condition</p> <p>→ medium impact on patient or public health</p>	<p>I</p> <p>Provides information to drive clinical management of a disease or conditions in a non-serious situation or condition</p> <p>→ low impact on patient or public health</p>	<p>I</p> <p>Provides information to inform clinical management for a disease or condition in a non-serious situation or condition</p> <p>→ low impact on patient or public health</p>

Source: based on IMDRF, 2014

3.3.3 Criterion: AI component

A fourth criterion for the taxonomy is whether DHT are AI-enabled and how autonomously they perform specific tasks. The EU regulatory framework for AI-enabled DHT is governed by the EU AI Act (2024) and the Medical Device Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2017/745). The AI Act addresses potential risks to health, safety, and fundamental rights of citizens and provides requirements and obligations regarding the specific use of AI for developers and deployers. It categorizes systems by risk levels: unacceptable (banned), high (including healthcare, requiring rigorous assessment), and low/minimal risk (requiring transparency). The MDR recognizes AI software as potential medical devices, classifying them from Class I (lowest risk) to Class III (highest risk). AI-enabled software typically falls into classes IIa-III based on function and potential risk of health deterioration (REGULATION (EU) 2017/745). Currently,

comprehensive guidance on AI regulation and its unique challenges is still developing in Europe and the USA (Boverhof et al., 2024).

The autonomy of AI systems in clinical care represents a key consideration for their classification. The American Medical Association (AMA) created an AI-taxonomy (2021), distinguishing three main categories of medical AI applications, reflecting increasing levels of independence (AMA, 2024):

- Assistive AI simply detects data, requiring full physician interpretation. This aligns with the "inform" dimension in the IMDRF framework, where systems provide information without analysis.
- Augmentative AI advances to data analysis and quantification but still requires physician interpretation of results, corresponding to the IMDRF's "drive" dimension where systems analyse to provide options.
- Autonomous AI represents the highest capability, independently interpreting data and generating conclusions, which aligns with the IMDRF's "make" dimension where systems take actions or decisions.

Within autonomous AI, three distinct levels exist, with varying healthcare professional involvement:

- **Level I:** The autonomous AI draws conclusions and offers diagnosis and/or management options, which are contestable and require physician or other quality health care professional (QHP) action to implement.
- **Level II:** The autonomous AI draws conclusions and initiates diagnosis and/or management options with alert/opportunity for override, which may require physician or other QHP action to implement.
- **Level III:** The autonomous AI draws conclusions and initiates management, which require physician or other QHP initiative to contest.

The HTA approach should consider the risk of AI component a DHT is based on. Despite the wide scope of the HTA Core Model, however, certain AI-specific assessment elements remain unaddressed (Alami et al., 2020). Challenges especially include those of assessing continuous learning AI technologies especially in terms of assessing risks, effectiveness, and safety of AI applications that change after deployment (Aquino et al., 2024). Therefore, we suggest differentiating between DHT based on static and adaptive AI components to be able to derive evidence requirements that apply to the respective group (with "no AI" as a third category) (Table 5). "Static" refers to DHT for which AI has been used during the research and development phases but which then results in a fixed algorithm, i.e. there is no learning element after the certification and assessment, while "adaptive" are those DHT which use AI on a continuous basis, resulting in any of the assistive/ augmented/ autonomous functions outlines above. Especially clinical effectiveness depends, for instance, on how the AI technology changes the existing workflows and how humans adapt to those changes. Some medical AI technologies change dynamically due to continuous learning (Boverhof et al., 2024). Adaptive AI systems are more complex to assess as they rely on the quality and reliability of feedback data, but they might also offer higher precision and responsiveness, making them highly beneficial in clinical applications. Adaptive systems may have to be evaluated also for their future learning capabilities, necessitating long-term evaluation approaches to understand their continuous improvement and impact on clinical outcomes AI is likely to generate.

Table 5. Criterion AI

AI component	Definition	Source	Examples
No	n/a	n/a	
Static (also fixed, pre-defined or frozen)	Using locked algorithms that respond in a predictable way: if input does not change, output will be the same each time Operate based on predefined rules and processes that do not dynamically adapt or respond to feedback	Aquino et al. 2024	medication delivery device that administers a fixed dose, regardless of the patient's current condition
(on-market) Adaptive (sometimes referred to as self-learning systems)	Using on-market retraining methods to adapt to new data or experiences, which could be in a periodic (batch) process, or could be (as methodologies advance), continuous. Changing on-market performance over time based on feedback, training data, or real-world usage, dynamically adjusting AI-models and processes	Petersen et al. 2021	AI-powered diagnostic system that constantly improves its predictions by analysing new patient cases

3.3.4 Combination of the criteria: purpose, risk and AI component

Figure 3 visualises the resulting taxonomy (with the risk criteria displayed separately, i.e. not in a matrix with 4 requirement levels).

Figure 3. Taxonomy of DHT in the logic of HTA

3.4 Practical considerations and refinement of the taxonomy

This is a first version of the taxonomy that was developed as part of the ASSESS project. The taxonomy was presented, discussed and refined after an expert workshop on October 24, 2024. Suggestions were made regarding the definition of DHT as a basis for the taxonomy and the need for a clear definition of AI. The taxonomy was also presented at a Round Table with members of HTA agencies on November 4, 2024 and an ASSESS DHT workshop held on November 6-7, 2024. All events were organized by ASSESS DHT members.

This developed taxonomy may be refined and adapted as new insights arise from ongoing developments in different countries. In addition, the taxonomy may be further refined through feedback from WP4, which will develop an overarching framework of criteria and guidance for the evaluation of DHTs in terms of an HTA manual for DHTs including a multi stakeholder toolkit. Furthermore, in WP5, case studies will be conducted to test and demonstrate the robustness and pragmatism of the assessment framework developed in ASSESS-DHT. Based on these case studies, the taxonomy will be piloted. The taxonomy will be piloted, and the categorization—based on the criteria of (medical) purpose, DHT-relevant dimensions of "risk," and the use of AI—will be reviewed, adapted, and modified, if necessary, as the project progresses. As part of the pilot test, we will examine how to handle situations where a DHT has multiple purposes or components. Our suggestion—that in such cases, the primary function should be decisive—can be tested. The pilot will also assess the suitability of the 3x3 matrix resulting in four requirement levels for practical use. Additionally, a decision rule for multi-component DHTs could be explored by applying the highest classification of any component as the overall classification.

This taxonomy provides a starting point, which will need to be complemented by wider HTA considerations which are in fact country specific considerations. For instance, it should be noted that the “vulnerability” dimension of risk is operationalised according to the health condition of the patient who will be the intended recipient of the technology, and the “directness” dimension of risk refers to the extent to which the technology guides or decides treatment. Together, they should help guide the evaluator in assessments about the clinical benefit-risk ratio associated with the technology for the health of individual patients, and the acceptable degree of uncertainty in the evidence. Notwithstanding, for country-specific HTA assessments, other dimensions of risk will need to be considered (such as financial risk and impact at a population level to name only a few).

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1 Questionnaire

Part 1 – Availability of frameworks/guidance documents/ guidelines to assess Digital Health Technologies (DHTs)

Question	Answer	Reference (link)
Does your agency use a classification/grouping system or a taxonomy to assign specific DHTs to groups/levels/tiers within the framework (guidance document/guideline) to determine specific assessment or evidence requirements/standards? If yes, please provide a reference/link and/or attach a copy of any unpublished document.		
Does your agency have any frameworks/guidance documents/guidelines that are used for assessing DHTs in general or for specific groups of DHTs?		
If yes, please briefly specify what document type it is and for which groups of DHTs and purpose the document is intended to use. If unpublished, please attach a copy of the document with your responses.	Document type:	
	Types/groups/tiers of DHT addressed:	
	Purpose of the document:	
Does your agency have any published or unpublished documents on evidence requirements or submission guidelines/templates for DHTs? If yes, please provide a link or attach with your responses.		
If no such document already exists: is your organization currently developing or adapting a framework (guidance document/guideline) to be used for assessing DHTs?		
If no DHT-specific framework/guidance document/guideline is available, what frameworks/guidance documents/guidelines does your agency consider appropriate for use in Health Technology Assessment (HTA) of DHTs?		

Part 2 – Currents status of assessed DHTs

Question	Answer	Reference (link)
Which digital health technologies have been evaluated by your agency so far? Please provide us with a link where we can access these documents or send us the evaluation documents by e-mail.		
Which digital health technologies are currently evaluated by your agency?		

Question	Answer	Reference (link)
If possible, please provide us with a link to a listing of these technologies or mention them directly.		

Part 3 – Current gaps and weaknesses in assessing DHTs

Question	Answer	Reference (link)
Do you see any gaps and weaknesses in the methods available to HTA bodies for assessing DHTs?		
How does your agency approach these challenges of assessing DHT?		
Which possible future approaches to overcome challenges in assessing DHTs do you suggest?		
Do different methods should be used at each stage of the lifecycle of a DHT? While we concentrate on the health technology assessment stage, there may be different methods for market access or post-marketing surveillance. Please shortly explain.		
Does your agency already use different methodological requirements for an HTA depending on the life cycle?		

Part 4 – Request for an expert specialized in AI

The Big Data Unit of the Andalusian public Progress and Health Foundation (Big Data-FPS) requests a nomination of an expert specialized in AI from your agency to participate in the following research.

Big Data-FPS will circulate questionnaire/s (as part of an online Delphi approach) to HTA experts specialized in AI. Questions included will pertain to the development of validation methods for AI-based decision support systems. The inquiries will focus on guidance for the validation of these systems, optimization of algorithms, and strategies for estimating predictive abilities using real-world data.

- Not-applicable: 'The scope of the questions is outside of our agency remit'
- Contact details: Name and e-mail address

Appendix 2 Identified taxonomies, classification, grouping of DHT

Organization: Title of the document	Purpose	Taxonomy/ classifications/ grouping/ categorization	Source
European Commission: Medical Device Regulation (MDR, Regulation (EU) 2017/745)	CE marking/ regulatory approval of Medical Device Software	<p>Risk class I, IIa, IIb, III</p> <p>‘Software, which drives a device or influences the use of a device, shall fall within the same class as the device. If the software is independent of any other device, it shall be classified in its own right.</p> <p>Software intended to provide information which is used to take decisions with diagnosis or therapeutic purposes is classified as class IIa, except if such decisions have an impact that may cause:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - death or an irreversible deterioration of a person's state of health, in which case it is in class III; or - a serious deterioration of a person's state of health or a surgical intervention, in which case it is classified as class IIb. <p>Software intended to monitor physiological processes is classified as class IIa, except if it is intended for monitoring of vital physiological parameters, where the nature of variations of those parameters is such that it could result in immediate danger to the patient, in which case it is classified as class IIb. All other software is classified as class I.’</p>	Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC (Text with EEA relevance.) [L 117/1]. Official Journal of the European Union 2017 May 5:1–175. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32017R0745
IMDRF: Software as a Medical Device": Possible Framework for Risk Categorization and Corresponding Considerations	Categorizing SaMD	<p>Grouping according to risk level in four classes: Risk level I, II, III, IV</p> <p>Two dimensions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. significance of the information provided by the SaMD to the healthcare decision: Treat or diagnose, drive clinical management, inform clinical management 2. state of the healthcare situation or condition: Critical, Serious, Non-serious. <p>The categories are in relative significance to each other. Category IV has the highest level of impact, Category I the lowest.</p>	International Medical Device Regulators Forum (IMDRF). 2014. Software as a Medical Device: Possible Framework for Risk Categorization and Corresponding Considerations. https://www.imdrf.org/documents/software-medical-device-possible-framework-risk-categorization-and-corresponding-considerations
IMDRF: Medical Device Software: Considerations for Device and Risk Characterization	Characterizations of medical device software (MDS) to promote and inform clear and accurate characterizations of MDS	<p>Information Grouping according to:</p> <p>Medical Problem and/or Objective (Medical Purpose, Intended Conditions/Diseases/ Disorders and Grade/Stage/Level, Intended Patient Population)</p>	International Medical Device Regulators Forum (IMDRF). 2024. IMDRF/SaMD WG/N81 DRAFT: 2024. Medical Device Software: Considerations for Device and Risk Characterization.

Organization: Title of the document	Purpose	Taxonomy/ classifications/ grouping/ categorization	Source
	to introduce a general strategy for characterizing software-specific risks that leverages key features of a comprehensive medical device software characterization	<p>Context of Medical Device Software Use (Intended User, Intended Use Environment, Timing Within Healthcare Task/Intervention, Role of Software Output Within the Healthcare Task/Intervention)</p> <p>Medical Device Software Function/ Use (Output Type, Input Source, Level of Task Automation, Degree of Clinical Autonomy, Intelligibility/Transparency/Explainability of Underlying Logic including the Algorithm/Technology used and How an Output is Reached, Destination/Target of Output)</p> <p>Medical Device Software Change Management (Degree of Learning/Change Management Autonomy, Domain of Learning/Change Implementation; Installation, Update and Error Correction Infrastructure)</p>	<p>https://www.imdrf.org/sites/default/files/2024-02/IMDRFSaMD%20WGN81%20DRAFT%202024%2C%20Medical%20Device%20Software%20Considerations%20for%20Device%20and%20Risk%20Characterization%20-%20final%20draft.pdf</p>
Digital Therapeutics Alliance: GUIDANCE TO INDUSTRY: Classification of Digital Health Technologies	Guidance: provide stakeholders with a better understanding of DHTs and create actionable categories that will accelerate the awareness, assessment, and ultimate adoption of various digital products	<p>8 subcategories to classify DHTs:</p> <p><i>Industry and Admin-Facing</i>: Non-Health System Software/ DH Solutions; Health System Operational Software</p> <p><i>Health care provider (HCP)-Facing</i>: Health System Clinical Software</p> <p><i>Patient-Facing</i>: Health & Wellness; Patient Monitoring; Care Support; Digital Diagnostics; Digital Therapeutics</p> <p>Defining DHT categories according to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - End User / Beneficiary - Intended Benefits / Claims - Regulatory Scrutiny - Strength of Evidence - Product / Intervention Type 	<p>GUIDANCE TO INDUSTRY: Classification of Digital Health Technologies.</p> <p>https://healthadvances.com/application/files/8316/9158/6634/health-advances-dta-dht-classification.pdf</p>
WHO: Classification of Digital Health Interventions v 1.0	Develop a mutually understandable language with which to assess and articulate functionality. Standardized vocabulary to identify gaps and duplication, evaluate effectiveness, and facilitate alignment	<p>DHT are classified around the target audience (based on the targeted primary user)</p> <p>Grouping according to ways the technologies support health system needs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interventions for clients, - Interventions for healthcare providers, - Interventions for health system and resource managers, - Interventions for data services 	<p>Classification of Digital Health Interventions v 1.0. A shared language to describe the uses of digital technology for health. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2018 (WHO/RHR/18.06). WHO-RHR-18.06-eng.pdf</p>

Organization: Title of the document	Purpose	Taxonomy/ classifications/ grouping/ categorization	Source
	across different digital health implementations		
WHO: Classification of Digital Health Interventions v 2.0	Refinement of a set of categorizations that links how digital health interventions (DHIs) embedded into digital applications and services are used to address personal and health system challenges and needs.	<p>Fours taxonomies: classification scheme organized around three axes: Health system challenges, Digital health interventions (DHIs), Digital Services and Application types.</p> <p>A taxonomy in each group describes the capabilities of digital technology that can be implemented to achieve objectives that are targeted toward respective groups.</p> <p>Grouping based on the targeted primary user.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interventions for persons, - Interventions for healthcare providers, - Interventions for health management and support personnel, - Interventions for data services 	Classification of digital interventions, services and applications in health: a shared language to describe the uses of digital technology for health, second edition. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2023, https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/373581/9789240081949-eng.pdf?sequence=1
<p>NICE: Evidence standards framework (ESF) for digital health technologies</p> <p>AQuAS: Health Technology Assessment Framework: Adaptation for Digital Health Technology Assessment: User Guide</p>	<p>Guidance</p> <p>Informed decision making for evaluators, decision makers and purchasers + information and support for companies</p> <p>Assignment of evidence level to tiers proportionate to the potential risk to service users for the DHT</p>	<p>Classification of DHT by intended purpose to stratify them into tiers (A, B, and C: Tier A (lowest risk), tier C (highest risk).) based on the potential risk to service users and to the system. Evidence level needed for each tier is proportionate to the potential risk to service users for the DHT in that tier.</p> <p>DHT in tier C are additionally split into four classification groups to align with the SaMD classification framework proposed by the International Medical Device Regulators Forum (IMDRF, 2014).</p>	<p>NICE. Evidence standards framework for digital health technologies (Published: 10 December 2018, Last updated: 9 August 2022). https://www.nice.org.uk/corporate/ecd7/resources/evidence-standards-framework-for-digital-health-technologies-pdf-1124017457605</p> <p>Segur-Ferrer J, Moltó-Puigmartí C, Pastells-Peiró R, Vivanco-Hidalgo RM. Health Technology Assessment Framework: Adaptation for Digital Health Technology Assessment: User Guide. Madrid: Ministry of Health. Barcelona: Agency for Health Quality and Assessment of Catalonia (AQuAS); 2023. https://aquas.gencat.cat/web/.content/minisite/aquas/publicacions/2023/framework-adaptation-digital-ha-user-guide-redets-aquas2023.pdf</p>

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HAUTE AUROTÉ De SANTÉ (HAS): Good Practice Guidelines on Health Apps and Smart Devices (Mobile Health or mHealth)	Guideline to improve evaluation lead to various assessment scenarios/standards mobile applications/smart device (low standard, medium standard, high standard).	Weighted risk matrix based on the main user and the main intended use declared for a mobile applications/smart device. Risk types: low criticality, medium criticality, high criticality	Good Practice Guidelines on Health Apps and Smart Devices (Mobile Health or mHealth) https://www.has-sante.fr/upload/docs/application/pdf/2017-03/dir1/good_practice_guidelines_on_health_apps_and_smart_devices_mobile_health_or_mhealth.pdf
ICER-PHTI: Assessment Framework for Digital Health Technologies,	Value assessment framework describes the conceptual model and associated methods that will guide assessments of digital health technologies within broader evaluative reports produced by the Peterson Health Technology Institute (PHTI)	Definition of evidence tiers for assessment of DHTs /effectiveness and safety) Evidence tiers are based on broad functional categories: (1) Self-Directed Health Management, (2) Professionally Directed Diagnostic and Prognostic Health Management, (3) Professionally Directed Preventative and Therapeutic Health Management and potential risk to patients: (1) low, (2) moderate, (3) high leading to four tiers.	ICER-PHTI: Assessment Framework for Digital Health Technologies. 2023. https://phti.com/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2023/09/ICER-PHTI-Assessment-Framework-for-Digital-Health-Technologies.pdf
U.S. Food & Drug Administration: Policy for Device Software Functions and Mobile Medical Applications	Guidance and recommendation for Industry and Food and Drug Administration Staff	Class I (general controls), Class II (special controls in addition to general controls), Class III (general controls and premarket approval) Regulatory Approach for Device Software Functions Description of device software functions: Software functions that are the focus of FDA’s regulatory oversight; Description of software functions for which FDA intends to exercise enforcement discretion	Policy for Device Software Functions and Mobile Medical Applications. Guidance for Industry and Food and Drug Administration Staff. 2022. https://www.fda.gov/media/80958/download
Institute for Drugs and Medical Devices (BfArM): Fast Track procedure for digital	Guideline for manufacturers, service providers and users (primarily addresses manufacturers in the application process for	Includes: Medical devices of risk class I, IIa, IIb [according to MDR], main function of the DiGA is based on digital technologies; the medical purpose must be essentially achieved by the main digital function; DiGA supports the detection, monitoring, treatment or alleviation of illnesses or the detection,	Social Code Book V, Verordnung über das Verfahren und die Anforderungen zur Prüfung der Erstattungsfähigkeit digitaler Gesundheitsanwendungen in der gesetzlichen Krankenversicherung (Digitale Gesundheitsanwendungen-

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health applications (DiGA)	statutory health insurance coverage decision)	<p>treatment, alleviation or compensation of injuries or disabilities; DiGA is used by the patient or by service providers and the patient together</p> <p>1) Differentiation between proven benefit of health care effect (medical outcomes/ patient relevant structural and procedural outcomes) and evidence not yet established → Decision benefit package (yes/no) versus Coverage with evidence development</p> <p>2) new since March/2024: Differentiation between MDR risk classes (1, 2a versus 2b) leading to different minimum required outcomes and study designs accepted for the assessment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - class 1, 2a: medical outcomes or patient relevant structural and procedural outcomes + retrospective comparative study designs - class 2b: medical outcomes + prospective comparative study design 	<p>Verordnung - DiGAV), Fast-Track-Verfahren für digitale Gesundheitsanwendungen (DiGA) nach § 139e SGB V. Ein Leitfaden für Hersteller, Leistungserbringer und Anwender Version 3.5 vom 28.12.2023. Attention: New version is not available yet.</p> <p>https://www.bfarm.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/Medizinprodukte/diga_leitfaden.html</p>
Haute Autorité de Santé (HAS)	Methodology guide about functional classification of digital solutions	<p>11 types of digital solutions classified in 4 levels (A, B, C, D), according to their intended use supplemented by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the capacity of the digital solution to take into account user/patient parameters (capable of resulting in personalisation of the response), - the autonomous or non-autonomous nature of the digital solution, making a distinction between technologies requiring human intervention to implement a therapeutic, screening or diagnostic action, and those generating this type of action themselves, i.e. without prior human intervention. 	<p>HAS (2021). Functional classification, according to their intended use, of digital solutions used in the context of medical and paramedical care. URL: https://www.has-sante.fr/icms/p_3238360/en/functional-classification-according-to-their-intended-use-of-digital-solutions-used-in-the-context-of-medical-and-paramedical-care?utm_source=chatgpt.com</p>

Appendix 3 Classification of a DHT in the taxonomy

Digital health technology: Components of Diawatch

Source: <https://proempower-pcp.eu/pcp-contractors/diawatch.html>,
<https://www.meteda.it/en/product/diawatch/>

DiaWatch: connecting People with Diabetes (PwD) and Healthcare professionals (HCPs), recording clinical parameters (e.g., blood glucose level), data exchange and real-time data monitoring by HCPs, physical training education sessions for PwD, AI-based life style change recommendations to PwD, support to risk prediction, motivation and assessment activities for HCPS... etc.

According to the manufacturer, DiaWatch has several components of the intervention:

- a sensing system platform
- an app for patients
- a (desktop and mobile) app for clinicians
- an interoperable cloud- based system

Stress test of ASSESS-DHT taxonomy (by Gregor Goetz and Yui Hidaka, AIHTA GmbH)

Directness: **Make**

- Data monitoring would have influences on patient management (e.g., medication changes), AI provides recommendations.

A certain difficulty remains when a DHT has many functions or components. Our (pragmatic) idea would be to use the "highest" classification of one (of the many) components for the general classification of directness that could be considered when using the DHT.

Patient Vulnerability: **Serious**

- “to mitigate long term irreversible consequences” e.g., Prevention of diabetes exacerbation, prevention of complications, etc.

Vulnerability of patients (state of healthcare situation/condition)	'Directness' Intention of using DHT-collected or -produced information for health care decisions (by health care provider or patient)		
	Make (treat or diagnose)	Drive (clinical) management	Inform (clinical) management
Critical	<p>IV</p> <p>Provides information to treat or diagnose a disease or conditions in a critical situation or condition</p> <p>→ very high impact on patient or public health</p>	<p>III</p> <p>Provides information to drive clinical management of a disease or conditions in a critical situation or condition</p> <p>→ high impact on patient or public health</p>	<p>II</p> <p>Provides information to inform clinical management of a disease or conditions in a critical situation or condition</p> <p>→ medium impact on patient or public health</p>
Serious	<p>III</p> <p>Provides information to treat or diagnose a disease or conditions in a serious situation or condition</p> <p>→ high impact on patient or public health</p>	<p>II</p> <p>Provides information to drive clinical management of a disease or conditions in a serious situation or condition</p> <p>→ medium impact on patient or public health</p>	<p>I</p> <p>Provides information to inform clinical management for a disease or conditions in a serious situation or condition</p> <p>→ low impact on patient or public health</p>
Non-serious	<p>II</p> <p>Provides information to treat or diagnose a disease or conditions in a non-serious situation or condition</p> <p>→ medium impact on patient or public health</p>	<p>I</p> <p>Provides information to drive clinical management of a disease or conditions in a non-serious situation or condition</p> <p>→ low impact on patient or public health</p>	<p>I</p> <p>Provides information to inform clinical management for a disease or condition in a non-serious situation or condition</p> <p>→ low impact on patient or public health</p>

AI: “Additionally, it incorporates an artificial intelligence-based application – DoctorPro – which exploits continuous machine learning models to profile the patient and make appropriate recommendations for diabetes treatment, exercise, and a healthy lifestyle.”
(cite: <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/429110-telemonitoring-for-people-with-diabetes>)

Classification (based on the limited information online accessible): adaptive, autonomy level: I